

Advancing in the physical fabrication of anthropomorphic breast phantoms

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BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Physical anthropomorphic breast phantoms are a key instrument for performing clinical and research work carried out in radiological departments¹⁻³. Major challenge and requirement in the field of X-ray breast imaging is the use of materials exhibiting similar X-ray absorption coefficients to those of breast tissue, especially of these to be used in a wide energy kilovoltage (kV) diagnostic range. There are several methods for assessing the appropriateness of a particular material. One such method involves fabricating sample materials and analyzing their attenuation characteristics. This analysis typically involves calculating linear attenuation coefficients^{4,5} and determining Hounsfield Units (HU) values through Computed Tomography (CT)⁶⁻⁹ experiments.

Previously, we reported on two methods for manufacturing of physical anthropomorphic breast phantoms utilizing fused filament fabrication technology. In both cases, modified 3D printers and a custom-developed software were used^{7,9}. The latter plays an important role in linking a series of breast patient CT scan images directly to the 3D printing process. One method involved the use of a single filament, a polylactic acid (PLA) one, with a constant filament extrusion rate for each voxel. This ensured that a precise amount of melted filament was extruded to every voxel corresponding to specific tissues, alongside a perimetric pattern to replicate smaller entities with more irregular shapes, such as glandular and tumor tissues⁷.

The second approach utilized two filaments to replicate the breast tissues, a PLA filament and a polypropylene (PP) filament. Each layer of the phantom was printed twice, once with PLA and once with PP. The extrusion rate for each material was meticulously controlled voxel-by-voxel, determined by the HU of the imported CT images.

Extensive preparatory work preceded the final printing of the breast phantoms, including the production of cubes with varying percentage filling. These cubes were subsequently scanned at CT facilities to assess the HU of each printed cube. Following the proposed methodologies, the phantoms were successfully produced and evaluated. However, the phantoms manufactured with these methodologies are specifically tailored for use with a particular energy of the X-ray beam. Thus, for each X-ray beam, a new breast phantom would need to be printed.

An ideal breast tissue-mimicking phantom should be created from materials demonstrating HU values close to these of the human breast tissue at typical diagnostic CT energies, especially when printed at 100% infill density. This pursuit extends to design of breast phantoms, necessitating the identification of materials that faithfully mimic tissue characteristics. Our recent investigation demonstrates that for creating an anthropomorphic breast phantom with distinct filaments representing different tissue components (such as adipose and glandular), an effective solution involved utilizing Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS) for breast adipose tissue and Acrylonitrile Styrene Acrylate (ASA) for glandular breast tissue. This study presents the results for a new physical anthropomorphic breast phantom, developed with these materials used with FFF 3D printers.

METHODS

In our recent investigation¹⁰, we experimentally studied the radiological properties of twenty-two 3D printing materials, used with FFF printing technology. We precisely determined the HU values of these materials by scanning test samples at a clinical CT within the range of incident x-ray beam with anode voltages of 80 kV and 120 kV. The CT numbers for each material were analyzed, and sets of filaments were identified as potential representatives of breast tissues: Thermoplastic copolyester (TPC, <https://formfutura.com/c/filaments/tpc-filaments/>) and ASA as potential representatives for glandular tissue and High Impact Polystyrene (HIPS) and ABS as representatives of the adipose tissue. In this study we chose to manufacture a breast phantom with ASA and ABS materials.

The computational breast model in this study is derived by applying segmentation techniques to a patient MR image⁷. The resulting digital phantom contains two distinct types of tissues: adipose and gland. The glandular tissue was assigned to the skin tissue to simplify the production model. Subsequently, one pair of identified suitable materials (ASA, ABS) was used to replace the corresponding breast tissues, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 7. Computational breast phantom (left) and a slice from the segmented breast (right).

In this study, an FFF dual extrusion 3D printer is utilized. The phantom was printed with X1-Carbon Bambu Lab printer. The selection of ASA and ABS, offered a distinct advantage due to their closely matched printing temperatures of 240°C¹⁰.

The assessment was conducted at a clinical CT unit, the Siemens Somatom Force, under three distinct tube voltages: 70 kVp, 120 kVp, and 150 kVp. A slice thickness of 0.5 mm was maintained throughout the scans, following the Thorax standard protocol. The distances between the source and the patient, as well as between the source and the detector, were 595 mm and 1085.6 mm, respectively. Image slices were sized at 523 pixels x 512 pixels, with each pixel measuring 0.285 mm by 0.285 mm, resulting in a width of 149 mm and a height of 146 mm.

RESULTS

Figure 2 displays the printed anthropomorphic breast phantom. The white material of the breast phantom corresponds to ASA, while the green material corresponds to ABS. The printing process required a total of 4 days to complete. As a preparatory measure, preliminary slices were printed in advance and subsequently evaluated using a radiography system, as shown in Figure 2. This approach aimed to visually ascertain whether the selected materials accurately replicated the radiological appearance of breast tissues.

Figure 8. Printed breast phantom and two printed slices. The radiography image on the right is the x-ray image of the slice, shown in the middle.

CT images, reconstructed from the 70 kV set of the scanned breast are shown in Figure 3. The values of the HU of the glandular representation were assessed across 10 slices within Regions of Interest (ROIs) located at the skin level. Each ROI measured 8 x 8 pixels. Meanwhile, the HU of the adipose simulation was measured through a single ROI, spanning 100 x 100 pixels, across 15 consecutive slices for each imaging set. Further on, to evaluate the average breast tissue, dedicated software designed for feature extraction from X-ray images was utilized¹¹ as illustrated in Figure 4. Results are summarized in Figure 5 for the three different kV imaging sets.

Figure 9. CT images, reconstructed from projections acquired at 70 kV.

Figure 10. Use of a dedicated software to measure the HU of the materials approximated by ASA and ABS.

Figure 11. Measured HU values, based on CT images of the breast phantom for the three different kV imaging sets.

DISCUSSION

The range of measured CT numbers for the replicated adipose breast tissue is between -116 HU and -60 HU for the incident beams of 70 kV-150 kV. The observed trend of increasing the HU with increasing the kV well compares with the one reported by Ma *et al.*⁶, where the authors modelled the HU of the adipose tissue in kV as a sum of the HU, measured at 120kV and a kV dependent difference function Δ . For the representation of glandular tissue, the measured values within the mentioned kV range ranged from 46 HU to 66 HU. Further experimental studies are necessary to validate the observed trend of increasing HU values of glandular tissue with higher kV settings. Ma *et al.*⁶ reported no energy dependence of the CT values with the kV for porcine leg, bovine tail and bovine ribs soft tissue samples. Other studies have shown that HU values for adipose tissue range from approximately -138 (at 80 kV)⁷ to -100 (at 120 kV)¹², while fibroglandular breast tissue is reported to be around 40 HU^{7,12} for incident beams ranging from 80kV to 120kV. However, data for glandular tissue are limited, hindering comprehensive comparison.

Currently, ongoing work is focused on producing three additional breast phantoms based on a combination of TPC and ASA with HIPS and ABS, and their comparison with the two methods proposed by the PHENOMENO team.

CONCLUSION

Utilizing ASA and ABS materials has proven effective in manufacturing an anthropomorphic breast phantom capable of reproducing radiological properties of the breast tissue across a broad spectrum of X-ray photon energies. Ongoing research activities will further clarify the optimal techniques and materials with the FFF printing technology for fabricating physical breast phantoms.

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The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Sarno A, Valero C, Tucciariello RM, *et al.* Physical and digital phantoms for 2D and 3D x-ray breast imaging: Review on the state-of-the-art and future prospects. Review. *Radiat Phys Chem.* 2023; (24) 110715; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radphyschem.2022.110715>
2. Bliznakova K. The advent of anthropomorphic three-dimensional breast phantoms for X-ray imaging. Review. *Physica Medica.* 2020;79:145-161. doi: 10.1016/j.ejmp.2020.11.025
3. Glick SJ, Ikejimba LC. Advances in digital and physical anthropomorphic breast phantoms for x-ray imaging. Review. *Med Phys.* 2018;45(10):e870-e885, doi: 10.1002/mp.13110
4. Ivanov D, Bliznakova K, Buliev I, *et al.* Suitability of low density materials for 3D printing of physical breast phantoms. *Phys Med Biol.* Sep 2018;63(17), 175020. doi: 10.1088/1361-6560/aad315.
5. Mettivier G, Sarno A, Varallo A, Russo P. Attenuation coefficient in the energy range 14-36 keV of 3D printing materials for physical breast phantoms. *Phys Med Biol.* Sep 7 2022; 67(17), doi: 10.1088/1361-6560/ac8966.
6. Ma X, Figl M, Unger E, Buschmann M, Homolka P. X-ray attenuation of bone, soft and adipose tissue in CT from 70 to 140 kV and comparison with 3D printable additive manufacturing materials. *Sci Rep.* Aug 26 2022;12(1):14580. doi:10.1038/s41598-022-18741-4
7. Dukov N, Bliznakova K, Okkalidis N, Teneva T, Encheva E, Bliznakov Z. Thermoplastic 3D printing technology using a single filament for producing realistic patient-derived breast models. *Phys Med Biol.* Feb 21 2022;67(4), doi: 10.1088/1361-6560/ac4c30.
8. Savi M, Andrade MAB, Potiens MPA. Commercial filament testing for use in 3D printed phantoms. *Radiat Phys Chem.* Sep 2020;174doi:ARTN 108906 10.1016/j.radphyschem.2020.108906
9. Okkalidis N, Bliznakova K. A voxel-by-voxel method for mixing two filaments during a 3D printing process for soft-tissue replication in an anthropomorphic breast phantom. *Phys Med Biol.* Dec 21 2022;67(24), doi:ARTN 245019 10.1088/1361-6560/aca640
10. Okkalidis F, Chatzigeorgiou C, Okkalidis N, *et al.* Characterization of commercial and custom-made 3D printing filament materials for CT imaging of organ body phantoms. *Results in Materials.* 2023;RINMA-D-23-00635(under review), <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4601778>
11. Marinov S, Buliev I, Cockmartin L, *et al.* Radiomics software for breast imaging optimization and simulation studies. *Phys Medica.* Sep 2021;89:114-128. doi:10.1016/j.ejmp.2021.07.014
12. Ruschin M, Davidson SRH, Phounsy W, *et al.* Technical Note: Multipurpose CT, ultrasound, and MRI breast phantom for use in radiotherapy and minimally invasive interventions. *Med Phys.* May 2016;43(5):2508-2514. doi:10.1118/1.4947124